

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

SIGNIFICANCE OF LANGUAGE SKILLS AND LANGUAGE ASPECTS IN SIGHT TRANSLATION

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Abstract

The article elaborates sight translation in terms of language skills. It is noted that knowledge of vocabulary, grammar and phonetics should be at a high level while making a sight translation. Reading and speaking skills are important in this type of translation. Since vision requires reading skill and interpretation needs speaking. There is no need to possess good listening skill since this skill has no function in sight translation. There is no the second person in sight translation to listen to. The translator might sometimes need to use writing skill in order to take some brief notes, namely dates, proper names, contractions.

Keywords: sight translation, language skills, language aspects, cultural level, interpretation

Introduction

Translation is a very intricate process. Translators are careful to consider the meaning of SL as shorthand in order to convey the corresponding meaning to the recipient. This process is defined differently by scholars and theorists. This is everyone's own perspective on how this process is carried out to convert ST to TT, taking into consideration all the variations at the linguistic, syntactic, semantic, and cultural levels. Essentially, translation is defined as the process of translating ST in one language into TT in another language. Therefore, we refer to the procedure for changing one form of SL to another form of TL. Babayev Javid underlines the difficulty of the translation: "As the architect imagines the design of a building prior to its construction, a translator or an interpreter should imagine the grammatical structure of the language while translating something" [1, p.117]

The most inevitable language skills in sight translation process are reading and speaking skills, Because the translator sees the text first, then interprets the information shown there. The translator does not need to have perfect listening skill since the translation is done by vision and speaking. The translator should have proficient pronunciation skills in order to utter the words fluently. Writing skill is sometimes used to take some important notes, particularly proper names, dates and abbreviations.

Main part

In the research work by Mauriel, the translation process goes through two important stages that enable the translator to arrive at an understood content. These stages are different from each. These phases include [7]:

- 1) Passive phase.
- 2) Active phase.

In the first stage, the translator must read the text completely, become immersed in the text, so that the mind is completely free from interference and can be attuned to and understood by the text. Then, all these extra-linguistic abilities can be the key to understanding the meaning of ambiguous texts. When this reading is successful, the text is remembered as a whole, and

associated with the reader's former background knowledge. In the second stage of this process, translators must become authors and use all their technical, cultural and rational skills to unleash their creativity. In this stage, translators can use all the knowledge and insight they picked up in the first phase, as well as all the signals. For the best results, these two phases should be run separately and not interfere with each other. Because it requires different skills and resources. From this perspective, Larson defines translation as the process of transferring the ST meaning of SL to TL through the transition from SL form to TL form, taking into account vocabulary, syntactic structure, and context. SL context and cultural variations to determine meaning in TL. In the end, we reconstruct these aspects in TL by finding the same meanings.

According to Shunnaq and Farghal, translation is considered as a transference process from one tongue into another one where two aspects are taken into consideration which are transference and sense [3]. The first aspect is related to rendering the ST into TT whereas the second one concentrates on conveyance of the meaning of ST by finding its relevant equivalent. May be, the most efficient definition of translation belongs to Lataiwish and Aziz who regard the translation as a stage of substituting a text in one language by another text in another language [6]. The so-called definition is considered to be the more obvious one since it doesn't go far in explaining how this process is carried out and what the interpreter followed to obtain such interpretation in the TL.

Sight translation is considered to be a mixed one of both interpretation and translation since it contains two crucial language skills and it is regarded as an essential instrument for training of interpreters and translators when they start their training interpreting program. Actually, SIT is easily determined as a process of interpreting a written text into an oral outcome. This definition points out that there are two main language skills involved in the process of translation and they possess an indispensable role in reformulating the ST. Weber claims that the students learn how to show the performance before the audience in order to render the

ST and improve their abilities in a quick coordination which becomes important in interpretation process afterwards. Weber thinks that it is a bit easier to understand and scrutinize the information in ST which is presented visually than the one introduced orally. He argues that this mode should be taught isolated from other modes of interpretation, as it represents an inseparable part between the both modes of interaction and is considered the basis for the development of interpreting skills.

While Moser-Mercer states that SiT is considered a useful pedagogical device that backs up students' performance in interpreting STs and preparing them for the next stage of rendering methods, as it is known as the first step to improve their interpreting skills [8]. Zheng points out that SiT involves replacing a message written in one language with a message delivered orally in another language, which demands the synchronization of reading skill and productive abilities when reformulating ST in one language into TT in another language [13]. In other words, Sadkhan points out that SiT implemented in three stages, beginning (sight reading) when the interpreter reads the SL written text with his eyes, then (comprehension) as he translates it with his mind, finally (transmission), when he orally translates this written text into the TL. In addition, all definitions clearly point out that this type of translation requires a definite level of mastery of the language skills involved in carrying out this type. It is also considered a stepping stone to two ways of interpreting - consecutive and simultaneous interpreting, and therefore most scientists have classified it into two different areas of translation and interpreting.

Modes of sight translation

Like other types of translation, SiT can be done in different modes, but the process appears to be similar as the translator cognitively engages with ST. In each mode, the interpreting must consider two critical steps being perception and production in which to accomplish this translation task. There are different types of SiT according to the degree of complexity. Broadly speaking, Ivars [5], Sampaio [12] and Sadkhan [11] put forward that there are five kinds of SiT in which the interpreter successfully manages the task. These are the following types:

1. Proper SiT: This mode manifests itself in the translation of a written text viewed for the first time and the translator has no time to prepare.

2. Prepared SiT: This mode is easier than the first one since the interpreter will have time to translate with sufficient preparation.

3. Consecutive SiT: In this mode, summary translation is carried out, through which the written interpretation is provided briefly. This mode is considered to translate sight and interpret sight.

4. SiT in consecutive interpretation: This is a process of oral reformulation of written input, which the speaker immediately and loudly pronounces.

5. SiT in simultaneous interpretation with text: This mode is considered the most complex, as it is carried out by simultaneous interpretation and visual translation of the written text. This mode can be implemented when the translator/interpreter owns a copy of

the written text. Hussein points out that in each mode, SiT is easily controlled based on two vital steps that any vision translator must follow to achieve a good ST rendering [4].

Sight translation process

There are two important aspects to consider (perception of the ST and production of the auditory message), these two cognitive processes are fundamental in all types of SiT.

Basic language skills in SiT.

Language skills have a direct impact on interpreters' performance in the interpretation process, so the effectiveness of communication, whether oral or written, depends on a person's language skills. Rich word stock, command of various sentence structures, clarity of thought and focus on the audience are essential for effective verbal communication. Verbal communication skills are writing and speaking, reading and listening. Numerous research works indicate that these skills may be used by interpreters in different proportions such as: writing 9% reading 16% speaking 30% listening 45%.

This process involves two basic language skills which play a direct role in the rendering of STs, in which the translator uses his two language skills (reading and speaking). These two skills are significant in the context of teaching any type of translation or interpreting because students need them to improve their performance and this development is directly related to these skills.

Reading skill.

This skill may be characterized as a means of increasing translator's knowledge of language features and their mastery of reading strategies. It can also improve their ability to understand and fit into the language-focused part of the course. A classic procedure for intensive reading is the grammar-translation approach, where the teacher works with students and uses the mother tongue to explain the meaning of the text sentence by sentence [9, p.25].

Colina claims that reading comprehension in the context of translation involves several levels of understanding, awareness of the reading process and the nature of reading, which are indispensable for anyone involved in interpretation [2, p.170]. Moreover, reading for translation is by definition much more complex than reading itself, and considerably more complex than traditionally recognized. For Colin, interpretation and reading are closely related. Nation points out four important steps a student can follow to develop vocabulary through the extensive reading method. These steps are:

1. Before reading the text, the student quickly skims through it and selects five or six words to focus on while reading. This has the effect of increasing the awareness of some words and thus making them more visible when you encounter them again in the text.

2. While reading, the student can collect new words which are repeated along the text and put them on word cards for later deliberate study.

3. A more formal follow-up is for students to report to the class a word they have come across in their reading – explaining what it means, how it has been

used in the text, its parts of speech, its etymology and any unusual features about it.

4. Using a dictionary while reading should also have positive effects.

Speaking skill.

This skill is one of the most essential language skill used in SiT. Students are required to be fluent in a text that visually translates and interprets it into oral communication in the TL. As other language activities, fluency, correct pronunciation, sufficient word stock and good grammar knowledge are indispensable factors for oral translation. A lot of pauses in speech, poor lexical resource, bad utterance and poor grammar knowledge are the signs of having poor language knowledge. They are interrelated with each other to some extent in some cases. Making intermittent pauses in interpretation process are the causes of poor grammar knowledge and lexical resources. It means that the lack of these language aspects has a negative and direct impact on fluency. If the interpreter has a good command in English or any other languages, he won't make pauses. As it is a special gift given by God, sometimes to own good grammar and lexical knowledge does not solve everything. The interpreter might have some memory problems to keep all information in mind. Despite perfect grammar knowledge and rich word stock, as well as precise pronunciation, the interpreter can experience difficulty in retaining several sentences in mind which have been produced by the speaker very fast. Besides, it may be caused by embarrassment and shyness in bigger auditorium. Excitement and alarm may result in poor interpretation, as well. For Nation and Newton [10, p.152] there are definite conditions which should be met to master fluency when a learner engages in a communicative act. These conditions are important for speaking and should be observed in order for the student's performance to gradually improve.

These conditions are:

1. The activity is meaning-centered. Students' attention is focused on communicating the message and exposed to the "real time" pressure and stress of ordinary meaning-oriented interaction.

2. Students take part in activities where all language items are within their former experience. This means that students work with mostly familiar topics and types of discourse using familiar vocabulary and constructions. These types of activities are called "practice" tasks since the knowledge needed to perform the activity is already within the students' experience.

3. The student is supported and encouraged to perform at a higher than normal level. This means that in a fluency activity, students should speak and understand faster, hesitate less, and use larger planned chunks than in normal language use. A fluency development activity provides some intentional movement toward a higher level of performance, often using time pressure.

Mean coefficient and percentage weight of items in mastery of these skills is an indispensable factor for successful completion of such a task. Students see SiT as a difficult task to learn without a clear teaching method and supporting skills to effectively convert ST in SL to TM in TL. The outcomes of the analysis show

that the students could realize the important role of language skills and how vital they are in developing their performance in SiT. While teaching SiT, it is important to take into consideration all the results, as they reflect the views of the students in the process of learning SiT. This work also studied the influence of commanding and acquiring the principles of SiT to prepare students for the next steps of interpreting, as SiT is the cornerstone of this type of interaction and in which students can tackle the translation difficulties they may encounter in interpretation process.

Conclusion

Finally, two important language skills were investigated to determine their importance in learning and teaching SiT. The analysis shows that these two language skills (reading and speaking) are required in teaching SiT and should be taken into consideration by both students and teachers. These two researchers advise all translation instructors and translation students to focus on developing language skills to improve students' performance in SiT, because without language skills, good performance cannot be achieved and their knowledge will be very insufficient in this type of translation.

This study concludes that translation students require an intensive course in language skills and how these skills are crucial and indispensable in learning translation and interpretation, as all strategies and techniques are closely related to these skills. Thus, students have to study language skills to see how the demands are placed on handling such demanding tasks.

The most important language skills depend on what type of translation the translator does. If the person does interpretation, he/she willy-nilly should develop his/her speaking and listening skills. Since the translator will listen and interpret the message in this way. But when a person does written translation, he should boost his/her writing and reading skills. Because the professional person in this job will need to write and see the text. Written text translation requires a deep attention and a great deal of word stock. Otherwise, the translator will experience hardships. Written translators don't need to improve their speaking and listening skills since they will not encounter these skills in written translation process. However, interpreters should practice on all skills. Because they may see a text in sight translation. Though they translate orally, they should own reading and writing skills as well.

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